

Ornithology by light levels today: dealing with a developing teenager

It is tempting to use solar geolocation as a technique for tracking wild animals. Geolocators are simple devices and thus very compact and cheap. They can be deployed in large numbers even on small-size animals. However, many of those who have used them have been disappointed by the low precision of the geographic positions obtained. Having turned 12 years of age, solar geolocation in ornithological research now encounters typical teenage problems. In a sense it has become more difficult to deal with than ever!

Geolocation by light-level entered ornithological research through studies of seabirds in the mid-2000s^{1,2}. Some years later, results of passerine and wader tracking with geolocators were published at almost the same time, in *Nature Communications*³, *Science*⁴ and *Wader Study Group Bulletin*^{5–7}. Although the accuracy of locations was much lower then, and the methods to estimate them were less user-friendly and somewhat *ad hoc*, it was a big breakthrough: at least we now got a rough idea where our birds went! This feeling was perhaps similar to the pride of parents watching a toddler taking its first steps: expectations are so low that any positive result brings overwhelming happiness!

At the age of seven, light-level tracking in ornithology entered primary school and learnt repeatability, transparency and calculus. The precision of the geolocator devices started to be tested across different habitats⁸, and the R-package

GeoLight⁹ specifically designed for repeatable and transparent analysis of solar geolocation data, appeared in 2012. Today, geolocation continues through secondary school, ‘learning’ new methods of analysis (BAStag¹⁰, FLightR¹¹), which together with more advanced devices, is leading to a higher level in the precision of position estimation.

However, this is also precisely the age when teenage problems materialize! Expectations of geolocators in terms of their accuracy and precision have grown, but the development of methodological and analytical techniques have struggled to keep up. At the same time, very precise positioning devices (e.g. GPS) have become smaller and more affordable and might soon compete directly with geolocators. So what is the future of this still-young method? I think geolocators only have a future if they keep declining in cost and are always considerably cheaper than other tracking devices. This would allow them to have a wider application for tracking birds, both in terms of sample size (many individuals) and repeatability (same individuals over several annual cycles).

Adolescence is the age of searching for a new identity and building a unique personality. This is the current challenge for solar geolocation. If it can achieve a new mature identity, potentially it can place itself in the position of being the main tool for research on large spatial-scale phenomena.

¹Croxall, J.P. *et al.* 2005. Global circumnavigations: tracking year-round ranges of nonbreeding albatrosses. *Science* 307: 249–250.

²Shaffer, S.A. *et al.* 2006. Migratory shearwaters integrate oceanic resources across the Pacific Ocean in an endless summer. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 103: 12799–12802.

³Conklin, J.R. *et al.* 2010. Breeding latitude drives individual schedules in a trans-hemispheric migrant bird. *Nature Communications* 1: 1–6.

⁴Stutchbury, B.J.M. *et al.* 2009. Tracking long-distance songbird migration by using geolocators. *Science* 323: 896–896.

⁵Minton, C. *et al.* 2011. Geolocator studies on Ruddy Turnstones *Arenaria interpres* and Greater Sandplovers *Charadrius leschenaultii* in the East Asian-Australasia Flyway reveal widely different migration strategies. *Wader Study Group Bulletin* 118: 87–96.

⁶Conklin, J.R. & P.F. Battley. 2010. Attachment of geolocators to Bar-tailed Godwits: a tibia-mounted method with no survival effects or loss of units. *Wader Study Group Bulletin* 117: 56–58.

⁷Clark, N.A. *et al.* 2010. The use of light-level geolocators to study wader movements. *Wader Study Group Bulletin* 117: 173–178.

⁸Lisovski, S. *et al.* 2012. Geolocation by light: accuracy and precision affected by environmental factors. *Methods in Ecology & Evolution* 3: 603–612.

⁹Lisovski, S. *et al.* 2012. GeoLight - processing and analysing light-based geolocator data in R. *Methods in Ecology & Evolution* 3: 1055–1059.

¹⁰Wotherspoon, S. *et al.* 2013. BAStag: Basic data processing for light based geolocation archival tags.

¹¹Rakhimberdiev, E. *et al.* 2015. A hidden Markov model for reconstructing animal paths from solar geolocation loggers using templates for light intensity. *Movement Ecology* 3: 25.

Massive deployment of geolocators on migratory waders can provide sufficient data for comprehensive studies on migration strategies and breeding biology on a near-continuous monitoring basis. Although massive deployment across several populations and/or regions is logistically (and financially) challenging, collaborative work is a clear possibility as it has recently been achieved for addressing geocator effects on the demographic rates of 16 Arctic-breeding waders¹². Another noteworthy aspect is that, despite relatively poor performance in positioning during migration, geolocation is so far the only reliable tool for remote monitoring of breeding waders^{13–15}. If it is attached to a wader's leg, a geocator becomes totally shaded during incubation, and therefore provides an incredibly clear representation of incubation patterns.

Therefore, collaborative studies on migratory connectivity, long-term monitoring of migratory routes, incubation patterns and other research topics are ways in which solar geolocation may blossom. However, this will only be possible if the growing quantity of geolocation data becomes available to the scientific community. At present, even the tracks collected within the wader community are not part of a centralized database. Several online databases, e.g. Dryad and Movebank (the latter focused on routine geolocation data upload), already facilitate the depositing of accessible data with different levels of permission granted by the data owners. Colleagues working with seabird tracking data and using multiple devices have already organized a database (<http://www.seabirdtracking.org>) which currently holds five million data points contributed by

A very short practical solar geolocation primer

Geocator tags are archival! This means you will have to recapture the bird to extract the information, and you will never get mortality data, so get to know how site-faithful your birds are and what is the re-trapping chance *before* starting a geolocation deployment programme. Devices are small (current smallest on the market is the 0.3 g Intigeo by Migrate Technology Ltd.) and can be attached either as a backpack or onto a leg flag or ring. At the time of writing, solar geolocators are the cheapest option for tracking studies, although small GPS archival loggers are similarly priced (~100 Euros). Devices only log light levels by time, with positions being estimated by the user through one of several available data analysis frameworks. All frameworks require data calibration for at least seven days with twilights logged at a known location. If deployed in the Arctic summer, consider sub-Arctic rooftop tag calibration before you depart to the field and do not expect locations during the polar day. Alternatively, calibration can be carried out after tag retrieval, but not if the battery is dead (so that is not advisable). Analysis can be done within proprietary software (e.g. Bastrak and Intiproc) or in the R environment using packages tripEstimation^{17,18} (replaced with SGAT), GeoLight⁹, BASTag¹⁰ or FLIGHTR¹¹. The precision of locations will be within a maximum of a few hundred kilometres, and will vary with geocator type, species biology, analysis technique and the length of time the bird remains in the same place (see Rakhimberdiev *et al.*¹⁹ for details). Methods of analysis are continuously being improved, so consider making your data available for future re-analysis. Locations provided by even the most advanced software are just estimates and are always subject to some level of uncertainty. Therefore no geocator-based track should be regarded as an absolute representation of a bird's movement. It is also important to avoid far-reaching conclusions based on single location estimates, as has occurred in the past²⁰.

¹²Weiser, E.L. *et al.* 2016. Effects of geolocators on demographic rates of 16 species of Arctic-breeding shorebirds. *Movement Ecology* In press.

¹³Burger, J. *et al.* 2012. Using geocator data to reveal incubation periods and breeding biology in Red Knots *Calidris canutus rufa*. *Wader Study Group Bulletin* 119: 26–36.

¹⁴Gosbell, K. *et al.* 2012. Geolocators reveal incubation and re-nesting characteristics of Ruddy Turnstones *Arenaria interpres* and Eastern Curlews *Numenius madagascariensis*. *Wader Study Group Bulletin* 119: 160–171.

¹⁵Loktionov, E.Y. *et al.* 2015. Study of incubation, chick rearing and breeding phenology of Red Knots *Calidris canutus rogersi* in sub-Arctic Far Eastern Russia aided by geolocators. *Wader Study* 122: 142–152.

¹⁶Lascelles, B.G. *et al.* 2016. Applying global criteria to tracking data to define important areas for marine conservation. *Diversity & Distributions* 22: 422–431.

¹⁷Sumner, M.D. *et al.* 2009. Bayesian estimation of animal movement from archival and satellite tags. *PLoS ONE* 4: e7324.

¹⁸Sumner, M. & S. Wotherspoon. 2011. *tripEstimation: Metropolis sampler and supporting functions for estimating animal movement from archival tags and satellite fixes*.

¹⁹Rakhimberdiev, E. *et al.* 2016. Comparing inferences of solar geolocation data against high-precision GPS data: annual movements of a double-tagged black-tailed godwit. *Journal of Avian Biology* doi:10.1111/jav.00891

²⁰Streby, H.M. *et al.* 2015. Tornadoic storm avoidance behavior in breeding songbirds. *Current Biology* 25: 98–102.

researchers from 120 institutions around the world¹⁶. Perhaps a good start would be to create an inventory of all wader geolocator projects, past and present. This would promote collaboration between researchers and would be useful for understanding migration ecology (e.g. connectivity, staging), and breeding season events; it would also be invaluable for wader conservation.

The next few years will be critical for the development of the ornithological use of light-level geolocators, but I hope that, with efforts by individual researchers to make data available for collaborative work, this field will become strong enough to survive into adulthood and will produce many more descriptive and synthetic papers.

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Geolocator project

The International Wader Study Group has set in motion a new project aimed primarily at communicating advances in geolocation and at hosting a database of studies to foster collaborative research among ‘waderologists’.

The project website will provide important baseline information for those setting up new geolocator studies, and will also be regularly updated with technical and analytical advances. We aim to provide geotracking maps of different species studied across the globe so that the most recent information can be quickly and visually shared. The project database will allow a rapid search for past and ongoing studies on waders across the globe. Data owners can be contacted if they wish to be listed and accessible, thus promoting the collaborative spirit of our group towards the understanding and conservation of waders. Those interested in setting up new studies and looking for advice about a species or technique will also find expertise on the database which will act as a knowledge exchange hub. In the (near) future, we will also be able to host tracking datasets with data access being owner defined, from private to freely available.

If you want to take part on this project please email us at: geowader@waderstudygroup.org.

We can either add your maps to our site, list your study or even do both!

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